

Effects of annulatophenone, annulatophenonoside, and acetylannulatophenonoside on brain synaptosomes and small cerebral vessels

Magdalena Kondeva-Burdina¹,
Paraskev Nedialkov³

¹ Department of Pharmacology, Pharmacotherapy and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Dunav str. 2, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria

² Institute of Neurobiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. Georgi Bonchev str., bl. 23, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria

³ Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Dunav str. 2, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Paraskev Nedialkov (pnedialkov@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 29 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 16 April 2026 ♦ Published 4 May 2026

Citation: Kondeva-Burdina M, Kadinov B, Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P (2026) Effects of annulatophenone, annulatophenonoside, and acetylannulatophenonoside on brain synaptosomes and small cerebral vessels. *Pharmacia* 73: e193535. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e193535>

Abstract

Three benzophenones (annulatophenone Hd15, annulatophenonoside Hd21, and acetylannulatophenonoside Hd22) isolated from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* Moris were evaluated for their neuroprotective properties. All compounds demonstrated significant neuroprotection in an *in vitro* 6-hydroxydopamine model using isolated rat brain synaptosomes. Annulatophenone Hd15 exhibited the strongest effect, enhancing synaptosomal viability and GSH levels by 35% and 25%, respectively, surpassing the positive control, silybin (25% and 15%). The lower activity of annulatophenonoside Hd21 is attributed to its sugar moiety, while acetylation in acetylannulatophenonoside Hd22 further reduced efficacy. The effects of the benzophenones on the contractility of the rat basilar artery (*a. basilaris*) were also evaluated, with only Hd22 increasing vascular tone.

Keywords

a. basilaris, benzophenones, contractility, *Hypericum annulatum*, neuroprotection, synaptosomes

Introduction

Representatives of the genus *Hypericum* (family Hypericaceae) comprise nearly 500 species classified into 36 intrageneric taxonomic sections. Its representatives range from trees and shrubs to annual and perennial herbaceous plants, adapted to habitats from semi-desert and dry areas to moderately moist and marshy environments. The genus is nearly worldwide in distribution, absent from regions such as southern Chile and Argentina, Antarctica, south-

ern oceanic islands, most tropical lowlands (except *H. japonicum*), and Arctic, subarctic, and alpine zones (Robson 1984). In Bulgaria, the genus *Hypericum* is represented by 22 species (Jordanov and Kožucharov 1970).

Hypericum annulatum Moris (sect. 27. Adenosepalum Spach) is a herbaceous perennial species native to the Balkan Peninsula, Sardinia, North Africa, and Arabia (Robson 1996). The earliest studies on the chemical composition of *Hypericum annulatum* date back to the late 1970s, when the xanthone gentisein and several fla-

vonoids, including hyperoside, quercitrin, rutin, kaempferol, quercetin, and myricetin, were identified (Kitanov and Achardjiev 1979). About two decades later, the 3-*O*-glucoside of gentisein (xanthohypericoside) was discovered—the first xanthone *O*-glycoside reported in the genus *Hypericum*—along with norathyriol, isomangiferin, isoquercitrin, and 1-3,II-8-biapigenin (Kitanov and Nedialkov 2000). Further studies have also established the presence of hypericin and pseudohypericin, with a total content of 0.066% of the dry mass of the aerial parts (Kitanov 2001). In 2001, the benzophenone *O*-glycoside hypericophenoside was isolated, together with annulatophenone. These compounds represent the first examples of simple oxygenated benzophenones identified in species of the genus *Hypericum* (Kitanov and Nedialkov 2001). Subsequent studies on this plant led to the isolation of three annulatophenone glycosides: annulatophenoside and acetylannulatophenoside (Nedialkov and Kitanov 2002) and neoannulatophenoside (Momekov et al. 2006). In addition to the simple oxygenated benzophenones, the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* have also yielded 5,7-dihydroxy-3-methylchromone (Nedialkov and Kitanov 2002), pinocembrin-7-*O*-glucoside (Momekov et al. 2006), and annulatamarin (Nedialkov et al. 2007). In other studies, benzophenone glycosides (neoannulatophenoside, hypericophenoside, annulatophenone, annulatophenoside, and acetylannulatophenoside) isolated from *H. annulatum* demonstrated cytoprotective potential in a K-562 cell model of epirubicin-induced toxicity (Momekov et al. 2006) and a protective effect against carbon tetrachloride-induced toxicity in isolated rat hepatocytes (Mitcheva et al. 2006). From the aerial parts of this plant, the prenylated phloroglucinol hyperatomarin has also been isolated, which has demonstrated antibacterial and cytotoxic activity (Šavikin-Fodulović et al. 2003; Momekov et al. 2008). Additionally, analysis of the essential oil from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* revealed that its main constituents are α -pinene, (E)- β -ocimene, undecane, myrcene, and β -pinene (Radulović et al. 2010). The benzophenones annulatophenone, annulatophenoside, and acetylannulatophenoside were also found in the methanolic extract of the aerial parts of *Hypericum mannulatum* (Zheleva-Dimitrova et al. 2012).

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the progressive loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, leading to a dopamine deficiency. Extensive biochemical evidence from human autopsies and animal models indicates that oxidative stress (OS) in the substantia nigra may drive dopaminergic neurodegeneration, though it remains unclear whether this stress is a primary cause or a secondary effect. Studies employing the neurotoxins 6-OHDA (6-hydroxydopamine) and MPTP (N-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine), which reliably produce oxidative stress and parkinsonian syndromes in multiple animal models, have greatly contributed to understanding dopaminergic neurodegeneration and the development of neuroprotective strategies (Grünblatt et al. 2000). It is well established that 6-OHDA is a highly reactive neurotoxin that readily undergoes au-

to-oxidation and monoamine oxidase-mediated deamination, generating hydrogen peroxide and reactive oxygen species (ROS). Its neurodegenerative effects are thought to be mediated by OS, leading to increased ROS generation and subsequent lipid peroxidation of neuronal membranes (Glinka et al. 1997; Grünblatt et al. 2000). Furthermore, both toxins induce an inflammatory response that leads to the proliferation of reactive microglia in the substantia nigra pars compacta. These reactive microglia are thought to mediate the inflammatory response due to their ability to generate large amounts of ROS (Isik et al. 2023). A similar pattern is observed in parkinsonian brains, with significantly increased levels of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-6, and TNF- α (Qu et al. 2023). Three key processes in which ROS are likely to contribute to blood vessel pathogenesis include hypertension, atherosclerosis, and structural changes in blood vessels. Most studies on the effects of ROS and OS in blood vessels have focused on the coronary, carotid, and cerebral arteries, with an emphasis on NAD(P)H oxidase activity and its impact on endothelial function (Touyz and Schiffrin 2004; Sun et al. 2016). The basilar artery supplies oxygenated blood to the cerebellum, brainstem, and occipital lobes. Given its essential role in maintaining oxygen and nutrient delivery to these critical brain regions, any disruption of its flow can result in severe neuronal injury, organ dysfunction, or death.

In the present study, the neuroprotective effects of three benzophenones isolated from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* Moris were investigated under *in vitro* conditions of 6-OHDA-induced oxidative stress, as well as their effects on the contractility of the rat basilar artery (*a. basilaris*).

The hypothesis is that the neuroprotective and vascular effects of these benzophenones are mechanistically linked through modulation of oxidative stress-related pathways, thereby preserving intracellular redox balance and membrane integrity. Given the central role of oxidative stress in both neuronal degeneration and vascular dysfunction, compounds that attenuate reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated damage may exert dual neuroprotective and vasomodulatory effects.

Material and methods

Materials, chemicals, and apparatus

The benzophenones, annulatophenone (Hd15) (Kitanov and Nedialkov 2001), as well as annulatophenoside (Hd21) and acetylannulatophenoside (Hd22) (Nedialkov and Kitanov 2002), were previously isolated from the methanolic extract of the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* Moris.

The reagents and buffer solutions used in the pharmacological studies, including HEPES (N-[2-hydroxyethyl] piperazine-N'-[2-ethanesulfonic acid]), as well as other chemicals such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), trichloroacetic acid (TCA), Percoll, 6-OHDA, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT), DTNB

(Ellman's reagent; 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid)), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), and silybin, were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂, CaCl₂·2H₂O, MgCl₂·6H₂O, NaHCO₃, NaH₂PO₄, KH₂PO₄, MgSO₄·7H₂O, D-glucose, D-sucrose, taurine (2-aminoethanesulfonic acid), and pyruvic acid were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

Experimental animals

The experiment was performed on old male Wistar rats. The animals were supplied by the National Breeding Center of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Slivnitsa, Bulgaria). They were housed under standard laboratory conditions in Plexiglas cages, with free access to food (53-3, produced in accordance with ISO 9001:2008) and water, and were maintained on a 12 h light/12 h dark cycle at a temperature of 20–25 °C and a humidity of 72 ± 4%. Food was withheld for 12 h prior to each experimental procedure. All experiments were conducted in accordance with Ordinance No. 15 on the Minimum Requirements for the Protection and Welfare of Experimental Animals (State Gazette No. 17, 2006), the applicable European regulations on the care and use of experimental animals, and Permission No. 304 (valid until 28 June 2026), issued by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency.

Isolation and incubation of rat brain synaptosomes

Synaptosomes were obtained from the brains of old male Wistar rats by repeated subcellular fractionation using a Percoll gradient, according to the method of Taupin et al. (1994).

Two buffers were prepared: Buffer A contained 5 mM HEPES and 0.32 M sucrose, while Buffer B contained 290 mM NaCl, 0.95 mM MgCl₂·2H₂O, 10 mM KCl, 2.4 mM CaCl₂·2H₂O, 2.1 mM NaH₂PO₄, 44 mM HEPES, and 13 mM D-glucose. Brain homogenates were prepared in Buffer A and centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The resulting supernatants were collected and subjected to a second centrifugation under the same conditions. The supernatants were then centrifuged three times at 10,000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C, with the final two centrifugations used specifically for the purification of synaptosomes.

Isolation was performed using a colloidal silica solution (Percoll), following these steps: First, a 90% stock solution of Percoll was prepared. Then, 16% and 10% Percoll solutions were made, and 4 mL of each were added to seven test tubes. Finally, 7.5% Percoll from the 90% stock was added to the sediment from the last centrifugation. The tubes were then centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C.

This resulted in three layers in the tubes: the lower layer contained mitochondria, the middle layer, at the interface between 16% and 10% Percoll, contained synaptosomes, and the upper layer contained lipids. The middle layers were carefully collected using a Pasteur pipette and pooled. Buffer B with glucose was added, and the mixture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 20 min at +4 °C. A buffer exchange was then performed, replacing the isolation buffer (Buffer A) with the incubation buffer (Buffer B). The result-

ing synaptosome-containing sediment was resuspended in Buffer B with glucose (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2014). The synaptosome concentration was 0.1 mg/mL. It was determined using the method of Lowry et al. (Lowry et al. 1951).

Synaptosomes were incubated under strictly controlled conditions to preserve their functional activity. Oxygenation was a critical factor for maintaining viability; samples were oxygenated with Carbogen (95% O₂ / 5% CO₂), and the incubation medium was maintained in a closed system to ensure stable gas concentrations and pH. Incubation was performed at 37 °C for 60 min. Benzophenones were applied at a final concentration of 10 μM, whereas 6-OHDA was used at 150 μM. Their effects were compared with those of silybin (10 μM).

6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity model on synaptosomes

This *in vitro* model mimics key aspects of neurodegenerative processes observed in Parkinson's disease. Dopamine metabolism and oxidation generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive quinones, which contribute to dopamine-induced neurotoxicity and neuronal degeneration (Stokes et al. 2002). Synaptosomes were incubated with 150 μM 6-OHDA and 10 μM benzophenones for 1 h.

Evaluation of synaptosomal viability using the MTT assay

Synaptosomal viability was evaluated post-incubation using the MTT assay, as previously described by Mungarro-Menchaca et al. (2002).

Determination of reduced glutathione

Reduced glutathione (GSH) levels were determined by measuring non-protein SH groups after protein precipitation with trichloroacetic acid. Following incubation, synaptosomes were centrifuged at 400 rpm for 3 min, and the sediment was treated with 5% trichloroacetic acid and left on ice for 10 min. Samples were centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min at 2 °C, and the supernatant was collected and stored at -20 °C. Prior to analysis, samples were neutralized with 5 M NaOH. Thiol groups were determined using Ellman's reagent, and the resulting yellow color was measured spectrophotometrically at 412 nm (Robyt et al. 1971).

Preparation of vascular tissue

Experiments were performed on native endothelium. Three modified Krebs solutions with varying mM compositions were used to study the contractility of vascular preparations.

The first type of solution was used for the isolation and mounting of vascular segments and consisted of NaCl 112.5 mM, KCl 4.75 mM, NaHCO₃ 25.00 mM, KH₂PO₄ 1.19 mM, MgSO₄·7H₂O 1.8 mM, CaCl₂ 0.00 or 0.16 mM, and glucose 11.5 mM. The absence of CaCl₂ in the solution was necessary to keep the vascular smooth muscle in a relaxed (dilated) state. This reduced the risk of mechan-

ical injury to the arterial wall during the preparatory procedures (Hessellund 2003). The second type of solution, intended for storing vascular segments, consisted of NaCl 118 mM, KCl 5 mM, CaCl₂ 2.5 mM, glucose 11.5 mM, taurine 10 mM, pyruvic acid 5 mM, and HEPES 25 mM (pH 7.4–7.5). The third type of solution was a physiological salt solution (PSS) used for contractile studies, with the composition varying depending on the blood vessel examined. For pre-contraction of vascular segments, the following solution was used: KCl 125 mM, MgSO₄·7H₂O 1.8 mM, NaHCO₃ 25.00 mM, KH₂PO₄ 1.19 mM, EDTA 0.03 mM, CaCl₂ 2.5 mM, and glucose 5.5 mM. For the basilar artery (*a. basilaris*), the solution consisted of NaCl 112.5 mM, KCl 3.5 mM, MgSO₄·7H₂O 1.2 mM, NaHCO₃ 25.00 mM, KH₂PO₄ 1.19 mM, EDTA 0.03 mM, CaCl₂ 1.5 mM, and glucose 5.5 mM.

Basilar artery (*a. basilaris*) isolation method

Within 10 min after euthanasia of the laboratory animal, the brain was removed from the cranial cavity. For this purpose, once the parietal bones had been removed, the brain was gently lifted in the frontal region with a spatula, thereby enabling transection of the cranial nerves and the optic nerve (n. opticus). This approach aimed to prevent damage to the meninges at the base of the brain and thereby preserve the basilar artery located in this region. Under a binocular microscope, the overlying meninges were carefully removed, and the basilar artery was subsequently meticulously dissected from the base of the brain in an ice-cold solution using fine scissors and forceps. The isolated artery was stored in ice-cold PSS solution for 20 min to preserve the vessel before being mounted on a wire myograph for analysis.

In vitro method for evaluating contractile responses in vascular segments

Mounting of vascular segments

Briefly, arterial segments (1.8–2 mm in length) were dissected from the surrounding tissues and mounted on two stainless steel wires (40 μm) in the same solution used for isolation. The preparations were secured with screws to steel jaws in the organ bath of a wire myograph (model 410A, JP Trading, Denmark), containing PSS solution for contractility studies (pH 7.4), aerated with 95% O₂ and 5% CO₂. One wire was connected to a micrometer to adjust the distance between the wires, and the other to a piezoelectric tension transducer. Residual connective and adipose tissue were carefully removed with scissors and tweezers. The dissection and mounting procedure took approximately 1 h at 2–4 °C (Mulvany and Halpern 1977).

Normalization

The normalization procedure was described in detail by Kadinov et al. (2025). Briefly, after mounting, the vaso-

lar segment was equilibrated for 30 min in a working PSS solution containing 2.5 mM CaCl₂ at 37 °C and aerated with carbogen (95% O₂, 5% CO₂). At the end of this period, the vessel preparation reached passive tension equivalent to that required to produce 90% of the maximum diameter (D100) at a pressure of 100 mmHg (Mulvany and Halpern 1977). The procedure started in an unloaded state, with the vessels being incrementally stretched by separating the wires. Each step increased the tension, and the vessels remained in this state for 100–120 s, undergoing a brief contraction before stabilizing at the tension level. The process was repeated until tension equivalent to 90% of the passive diameter was achieved, at an effective pressure of 13.3 kPa (100 mmHg) (Mulvany and Halpern 1977; Corcoran et al. 2014). Normalization accounts for differences in segment length and diameter, allowing analysis of vessels under equal intravascular pressures, as in biological systems (Shirasawa and Benoit 2003).

After normalization, the vascular segments were incubated for 30 min before the experiment. The viability of the preparation and the condition of the endothelium were assessed during the experiments. Viability was evaluated by successive applications of PSS for pre-contraction. Functionally intact endothelium was confirmed by acetylcholine (ACh)-induced relaxation (10⁻⁵ M) applied during the plateau phase of the contraction induced by 125 mM K. During the real experiment, the isolated *a. basilaris* was incubated for 1 h with the benzophenones.

Statistical analysis

Data from isolated synaptosomes were analyzed using MEDCALC software, with statistical significance assessed by the non-parametric Mann–Whitney test at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$. Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) from three independent experiments, each performed in triplicate. Contractility data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA, with means ± standard error of the mean reported for preparations from individual animals. Statistical significance was determined using Student's *t*-test for paired comparisons and the Tukey–Kramer multiple comparison test for group comparisons ($p < 0.05$). Data processing, graphing, and figure preparation were performed using GraphPad InStat (v2.04 and v3.02), Origin Pro 7.5 PRO, CorelDRAW, and MyoData v2.02.

Prior to statistical analysis, data distribution was assessed, and appropriate parametric or non-parametric tests were applied accordingly. The value of *n* represents the number of independent biological replicates (animals), unless otherwise specified.

Results and discussion

Three benzophenones—annulatophenone Hd15 (Kitanov and Nedialkov 2001), annulatophenonoside Hd21, and acetylannulatophenonoside Hd22 (Nedialkov and Kitanov 2002) (Fig. 1)—previously isolated from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* Moris were tested for neuropro-

Figure 1. Benzophenones from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* Moris.

tective activity under *in vitro* conditions of 6-OHDA-induced oxidative stress, as well as for their effects on the contractility of the rat basilar artery (*a. basilaris*).

Effects of benzophenones Hd15, Hd21, Hd22, and silybin on isolated rat brain synaptosomes

Alongside other *in vitro* brain models, such as brain slices and primary neuronal cultures, isolated presynaptic terminals—synaptosomes—represent a well-established tool for the molecular-level investigation of synaptic function (Ahmad and Liu 2020). In this study, the neuroprotective properties of three benzophenones (annulatophenone Hd15, annulatophenonoside Hd21, and acetylannulatophenonoside Hd22) on isolated rat brain synaptosomes were evaluated. The synaptosomes were prepared from rat brains using a Percoll-based density gradient method, a widely employed approach for obtaining highly purified and functional presynaptic terminals suitable for pharmacological and biochemical analysis (Taupin et al. 1994).

Effects of benzophenones Hd15, Hd21, Hd22, and silybin administered alone

When applied alone, at a concentration of 10 μM , the tested benzophenones and silybin did not exhibit a statistically significant neurotoxic effect on isolated rat brain synaptosomes. They did not alter synaptosomal viability or the level of reduced glutathione (GSH) compared with the control (non-treated synaptosomes) (Fig. 2).

Effects of benzophenones Hd15, Hd21, Hd22, and silybin in a 6-OHDA-induced oxidative stress model

The treatment of isolated rat brain synaptosomes with 6-OHDA is a well-established *in vitro* model for investigating the mechanisms underlying neurodegeneration in Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases. This model enables the detection of early damage in nerve terminals and the evaluation of oxidative stress under controlled conditions. The neurotoxicity of 6-OHDA is primarily attributed to its

auto-oxidation and mitochondrial metabolism, processes that generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), including superoxide anion, hydrogen peroxide, and hydroxyl radicals, leading to oxidative stress and neuronal damage (Stokes et al. 2002; Tamuli et al. 2025). Additionally, reactive quinone derivatives (*p*-quinones) are produced, further intensifying oxidative stress and causing damage to cellular components (Stokes et al. 2002). The reactive intermediate products are believed to covalently interact with molecules in nerve terminals, leading to their permanent inactivation and degeneration. Additionally, oxidative stress activates signaling pathways associated with apoptosis and cell death, making the 6-OHDA model particularly suitable for studying neuronal damage and potential neuroprotective strategies (Dias et al. 2013).

When administered alone at a concentration of 150 μM , 6-OHDA exhibits a pronounced and statistically significant neurotoxic effect compared to the control (untreated synaptosomes), reducing synaptosomal viability by 55% and GSH levels by 50% (Fig. 3). In a 6-OHDA (150 μM)-induced oxidative stress model, at a concentration of 10 μM , the tested benzophenones and silybin demonstrated a statistically significant neuroprotective effect on isolated synaptosomes. They effectively preserved synaptosomal viability and GSH levels compared to the toxic agent (Fig. 3). Among them, annulatophenone (Hd15) exhibited the most pronounced effect, surpassing both Hd21 and Hd22, and was also statistically significantly more potent than silybin.

Compared to the toxic agent, the tested benzophenones preserved synaptosomal viability by 15–35%. Annulatophenone Hd15, annulatophenonoside Hd21, and acetylannulatophenonoside Hd22 prevented the 6-OHDA-induced decrease in synaptosomal viability by 35%, 20%, and 15%, respectively. Notably, annulatophenone Hd15 preserved synaptosomal viability more effectively than the positive control, silybin (25%) (Fig. 3).

Both benzophenones, annulatophenonoside Hd21 and acetylannulatophenonoside Hd22, prevented 6-OHDA-induced GSH depletion by 10%. The most active compound was again annulatophenone Hd15, which preserved GSH levels by 25% compared to the 6-OHDA group (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Effects of benzophenones Hd15, Hd21, Hd22, and silybin, administered alone at a concentration of 10 μ M, on synaptosomal viability and GSH levels.

Figure 3. Effects of benzophenones Hd15, Hd21, Hd22, and silybin on synaptosomal viability and GSH levels in a model of 6-OHDA-induced oxidative stress. *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated synaptosomes); + $P < 0.05$; ++ $P < 0.01$ vs. toxic agent 6-OHDA; # $P < 0.05$ vs. silybin (S).

The results of the present study showed that, in a model of 6-OHDA-induced oxidative stress on isolated rat brain synaptosomes, the most active benzophenone was annulato-phenone Hd15, which preserved synaptosomal viability and GSH levels by 35% and 25%, respectively, exceeding the activity of the positive control, silybin (25% and 15%, respectively). The lower activity of Hd21 is likely due to the presence of a sugar moiety in its structure, and acetylation of the sugar, as in acetylannulato-phenonoside Hd22, further reduces its activity.

The observed differences in activity among the tested benzophenones may be rationalized in terms of structure-activity relationships. The higher activity of annulato-phenone (Hd15), compared to its glycosylated derivatives (Hd21 and Hd22), is likely associated with its increased lipophilicity, which may facilitate membrane permeability and interaction with lipid bilayers. This, in turn, could enhance its ability to stabilize synaptosomal membranes

under oxidative stress conditions. In contrast, the presence of a sugar moiety may reduce membrane permeability, thereby limiting intracellular availability and biological activity. Additional acetylation of the glycoside, as in Hd22, may further modulate its physicochemical properties and reduce its antioxidant efficiency.

From a mechanistic perspective, the neuroprotective effects observed in the 6-OHDA model are consistent with the ability of benzophenones to act as redox-active molecules capable of scavenging reactive oxygen species and preserving endogenous antioxidant systems, such as reduced GSH. Maintenance of GSH levels is particularly important in neuronal systems, where oxidative stress plays a central role in the initiation of lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and mitochondrial dysfunction. Thus, the preservation of synaptosomal viability and GSH levels suggests that these compounds may interfere with early oxidative events leading to neuronal damage.

In vitro evaluation of the effects of benzophenones Hd15, Hd21, and Hd22 on small cerebral vessels

Vascular parkinsonism is a condition characterized by parkinsonian symptoms resulting from cerebrovascular pathology. The movement symptoms of vascular parkinsonism typically cause unsteadiness during walking. Vascular parkinsonism is relatively rare. It represents 4.4%–12% of all cases of parkinsonism (Mehanna and Jankovic 2013).

Movement disorders can occur as a primary (idiopathic) or genetic disease, as a manifestation of an underlying neurodegenerative disorder, or secondary to a wide range of neurological or systemic diseases. Cerebrovascular diseases represent up to 22% of secondary movement disorders, and involuntary movements develop after 1–4% of strokes. Post-stroke movement disorders can manifest as parkinsonism or a wide range of hyperkinetic movement disorders, including chorea, ballism, athetosis, dystonia, tremor, myoclonus, stereotypies, and akathisia. Some of these disorders occur immediately after acute stroke, whereas others can develop later, and yet others represent delayed-onset progressive movement disorders. These movement disorders have been encountered in patients with ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes, subarachnoid hemorrhage, cerebrovascular malformations, and dural arteriovenous fistula affecting the basal ganglia, their connections, or both (Mehanna and Jankovic 2013).

In preliminary studies, it was found that annulatophenone Hd15 and annulatophenone Hd21 did not exhibit a statistically significant effect on the contractility of small cerebral vessels. Only acetylannulatophenone Hd22 showed a statistically significant effect on the basilar artery (Figs 4, 5).

The results showed that acetylannulatophenone Hd22, at the applied concentration (10 μ M), increases vascular tone in the smooth muscle of basilar artery segments. This response was characterized by a transient elevation in tone (Fig. 4), followed by stabilization at a lower level. The effect was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$, $n = 6$), with an average increase in vascular tone of 24% (Fig. 5).

The vascular effects observed in the present study, although limited to Hd22, may also be interpreted within the context of oxidative stress-mediated regulation of vascular tone. Reactive oxygen species are known to modulate vascular smooth muscle contractility through multiple mechanisms, including alterations in calcium signaling, nitric oxide bioavailability, and redox-sensitive ion channels (Touyz and Schiffrin 2004; Drummond et al. 2011; Förstermann and Sessa 2012; Griendling et al. 2016). In this context, the increase in basilar artery tone induced by Hd22 may reflect a compound-specific interaction with vascular signaling pathways, potentially related to its modified polarity and reduced antioxidant capacity compared to Hd15.

Importantly, the interplay between neuronal and vascular components is increasingly recognized within the

Figure 4. Effect of acetylannulatophenone Hd22 (10 μ M) on the tension of *a. basilaris*.

Figure 5. Statistical analysis of vascular tension in segments treated with acetylannulatophenone Hd22 in comparison with control.

concept of the neurovascular unit, in which oxidative stress is a common pathogenic factor. Therefore, the combined evaluation of neuroprotective and vascular effects provides a more integrated perspective on the biological activity of these benzophenones.

These findings suggest that the neuroprotective and antioxidant effects of the benzophenones (Hd15, Hd21, and Hd22), isolated from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum*, are likely associated, on one hand, with the preservation of the cellular protector and free radical scavenger reduced glutathione (GSH) and, on the other hand, with potential membrane stabilization, as reflected by the maintenance of synaptosomal viability. These results are consistent with previous reports on the neuroprotective activity of benzophenones isolated from *Hypericum aucheri* in a 6-OHDA-induced oxidative stress model (Marinov et al. 2024). This is the first study to investigate the effects of these benzophenones on rat basilar artery contractility. In this study, only Hd22 increased basilar artery tone.

Conclusion

Three benzophenones (annulatophenone Hd15, annulatophenone Hd21, and acetylannulatophenone Hd22) isolated from the aerial parts of *Hypericum annulatum* were investigated for their neuroprotective activity. All tested compounds showed statistically significant neuroprotective effects on isolated rat brain synaptosomes in a 6-OHDA *in vitro* model. The most active benzophenone was annulatophenone Hd15, which preserved synaptosomal viability and GSH levels by 35% and 25%, respectively, exceeding the activity of the positive control, silybin (25% and 15%, respectively). The effects of the benzophenones on the contractility of the rat basilar artery (*a. basilaris*) were also evaluated, and only acetylannulatophenone Hd22 induced an increase in basilar artery tone.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

References

- Ahmad F, Liu P (2020) Synaptosome as a tool in Alzheimer's disease research. *Brain research* 1746: 147009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2020.147009>
- Corcoran JJ, Nicholson C, Sweeney M, Charnock JC, Robson SC, Westwood M, Taggart MJ (2014) Human uterine and placental arteries exhibit tissue-specific acute responses to 17 β -estradiol and estrogen-receptor-specific agonists. *Molecular Human Reproduction* 20(5): 433–441. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molehr/gat095>
- Dias V, Junn E, Mouradian MM (2013) The role of oxidative stress in Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Parkinson's disease* 3(4): 461–491. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JPD-130230>
- Drummond GR, Selemidis S, Griendling KK, Sobey CG (2011) Combating oxidative stress in vascular disease: NADPH oxidases as therapeutic targets. *Nature reviews Drug discovery* 10(6): 453–471. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3403>
- Förstermann U, Sessa WC (2012) Nitric oxide synthases: regulation and function. *European Heart Journal* 33(7): 829–837. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehr304>
- Glinka Y, Gassen M, Youdim MBH (1997) Mechanism of 6-hydroxydopamine neurotoxicity. *Journal Neural Transmission (suppl)* 50: 55–66. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-6842-4_7
- Griendling KK, Touyz RM, Zweier JL, Dikalov S, Chilian W, Chen YR, Harrison DG, Bhatnagar A (2016) Measurement of reactive oxygen species, reactive nitrogen species, and redox-dependent signaling in the cardiovascular system: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation research* 119(5): e39–e75. <https://doi.org/10.1161/RES.0000000000000110>
- Grünblatt E, Mandel S, Youdim MB (2000) MPTP and 6-hydroxydopamine-induced neurodegeneration as models for Parkinson's disease: neuroprotective strategies. *Journal of Neurology* 247(Suppl 2): II95–II102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/PL00022909>
- Hessellund A, Jeppesen P, Aalkjaer C, Bek T (2003) Characterization of vasomotion in porcine retinal arterioles. *Acta Ophthalmologica Scandinavica* 81(3): 278–282. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0420.2003.00063.x>
- Isik S, Yeman Kiyak B, Akbayir R, Seyhali R, Arpacı T (2023) Microglia mediated neuroinflammation in Parkinson's Disease 12(7): 1012. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells12071012>
- Jordanov D, Kožucharov S (1970) *Hypericum* L. In: Jordanov D (Eds) *Flora of R. P. Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 224–264.
- Kadinov BG, Mateeva A, Georgieva M, Mitkov Y, Zlatkov A, Kondeva-Burdina M (2025) Effect of pyrrole and xanthine derivatives on the contractility of *a. basilaris*. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e141976>
- Kitanov G, Achtardjiev C (1979) Isolation of gentisein from *Hypericum degenii* Bornm. *Pharmazie* 34(7): 447–8.

Experiments on animals: Permission No. 304 (valid until 28 June 2026), issued by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This research was funded by the European Union—NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, contract number BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Magdalena Kondeva-Burdina <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6776-0870>

Zlatina Kokanova-Nedialkova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1553-6428>

Paraskev Nedialkov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5640-6120>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- Kitanov GM (2001) Hypericin and pseudohypericin in some *Hypericum* species. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology* 29(2): 171–178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0305-1978\(00\)00032-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0305-1978(00)00032-6)
- Kitanov GM, Nedialkov PT (2000) Xanthohypericoside, a new xanthone-O-glucoside from *Hypericum annulatum* *Pharmazie* 55(5): 397–398.
- Kitanov GM, Nedialkov PT (2001) Benzophenone O-glucoside, a biogenic precursor of 1,3,7-trioxygenated xanthenes in *Hypericum annulatum*. *Phytochemistry* 57(8): 1237–1243. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422\(01\)00194-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(01)00194-7)
- Kondeva-Burdina M, Krasteva I, Mitcheva M (2014) Effects of rhamnocitrin 4- β -D-galactopyranoside, isolated from *Astragalus hamosus* on toxicity models *in vitro*. *Pharmacognosy Magazine* 10(Suppl 3): S487. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-1296.139778>
- Lowry O, Rosebrough N, Farr AL, Randall RJ (1951) Protein measurement with the Folin phenol reagent. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 193(1): 265–275. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258\(19\)52451-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(19)52451-6)
- Marinov T, Kondeva-Burdina M, Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov PT (2024) Phenolic constituents from *Hypericum aucheri* Jaub & Spach—Isolation, identification, and preliminary evaluation for hMAO-A/B and neuroprotective activity. *Chemistry* 6(6): 1535–1551. <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemistry6060093>
- Mehanna R, Jankovic J (2013) Movement disorders in cerebrovascular disease. *Lancet Neurology* 12(6): 597–608. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(13\)70057-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(13)70057-7)
- Mitcheva M, Kondeva M, Vitcheva V, Nedialkov P, Kitanov G (2006) Effect of benzophenones from *Hypericum annulatum* on carbon tetrachloride-induced toxicity in freshly isolated rat hepatocytes. *Redox Report* 11(1): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1179/135100006x100968>
- Momekov G, Ferdinandov D, Zheleva-Dimitrova D, Nedialkov P, Girreser U, Kitanov G (2008) Cytotoxic effects of hyperatomarin, a prenylated phloroglucinol from *Hypericum annulatum* Moris subsp. *annulatum*, in a panel of malignant cell lines. *Phytomedicine* 15(11): 1010–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2008.04.008>
- Momekov G, Nedialkov PT, Kitanov GM, Zheleva-Dimitrova D, Tzanova T, Girreser U (2006) Cytoprotective effects of 5 benzophenones and a xanthone from *Hypericum annulatum* in models of epirubicin-induced cytotoxicity: SAR-analysis and mechanistic investigations. *Medicinal Chemistry* 2(4): 377–84. <https://doi.org/10.2174/157340606777724103>
- Mulvany MJ, Halpern W (1977) Contractile properties of small arterial resistance vessels in spontaneously hypertensive and normotensive rats. *Circulation research* 41(1): 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.41.1.19>
- Mungarro-Menchaca X, Ferrera P, Morán J, Arias C (2002) β -Amyloid peptide induces ultrastructural changes in synaptosomes and potentiates mitochondrial dysfunction in the presence of ryanodine. *Journal of Neuroscience Research* 68(1): 89–96. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jnr.10193>
- Nedialkov PT, Kitanov GM (2002) Two benzophenone O-arabinosides and a chromone from *Hypericum annulatum*. *Phytochemistry* 59(8): 867–871. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422\(01\)00484-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(01)00484-8)
- Nedialkov PT, Zheleva-Dimitrova D, Girreser U, Kitanov GM (2007) A new isocoumarin from *Hypericum annulatum*. *Natural Product Research* 21(12): 1056–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786410701567762>
- Qu Y, Li J, Qin Q, Wang D, Zhao J, An K, Mao Z, Min Z, Xiong Y, Li J, Xue Z (2023) A systematic review and meta-analysis of inflammatory biomarkers in Parkinson's disease. *npj Parkinsons Disease* 9: 18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-023-00449-5>
- Radulović N, Đorđević A, Palić R, Zlatković B (2010) Essential oil composition of *Hypericum annulatum* Moris (Hypericaceae) from Serbia. *Journal of Essential Oil Research* 22(6): 619–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.2010.9700416>
- Robson NKB (1984) Studies in the Genus *Hypericum* L. (Guttiferae): 3. Sections: 1. Campyloporus to: 6a. Umbraculoides. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum (Botany)* 12(4): 163–325.
- Robson NKB (1996) Studies in the genus *Hypericum* L. (Guttiferae). 6. Sections 20. Myriandra to 28. Elodes. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum (Botany)* 26(2): 75–217.
- Robyt JF, Ackerman RJ, Chittenden CG (1971) Reaction of protein disulfide groups with Ellman's reagent: A case study of the number of sulfhydryl and disulfide groups in *Aspergillus oryzae* α -amylase, papain, and lysozyme. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics* 147(1): 262–269. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-9861\(71\)90334-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-9861(71)90334-1)
- Šavikin-Fodulović K, Aljančić I, Vajs V, Menković N, Macura S, Gojčić G, et al. (2003) Hyperatomarin, an antibacterial prenylated phloroglucinol from *Hypericum atomarium* ssp. *degenii*. *Journal of Natural Products* 66(9): 1236–8. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np030131o>
- Shirasawa Y, Benoit JN (2003) Stretch-induced calcium sensitization of rat lymphatic smooth muscle. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 285(6): H2573–H2577. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00002.2003>
- Stokes AH, Freeman WM, Mitchell SG, Burnette TA, Hellmann GM, Vrana KE (2002) Induction of GADD45 and GADD153 in neuroblastoma cells by dopamine-induced toxicity. *Neurotoxicology* 23(6): 675–84. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-813X\(02\)00093-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-813X(02)00093-1)
- Sun QA, Runge MS, Madamanchi NR (2016) Oxidative stress, NADPH oxidases, and arteries. *Hamostaseologie* 36(2): 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.5482/HAMO-14-11-0076>
- Tamuli R, Mellick GD, Schirra HJ, Feng Y (2025) Mode of action of toxin 6-hydroxydopamine in SH-SY5Y using NMR metabolomics. *Molecules* 30(16): 3352. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30163352>
- Taupin P, Zini S, Cesselin F, Ben-Ari Y, Roisin MP (1994) Subcellular fractionation on Percoll gradient of mossy fiber synaptosomes: morphological and biochemical characterization in control and degranulated rat hippocampus. *Journal of Neurochemistry* 62(4): 1586–1595. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1471-4159.1994.62041586.x>
- Touyz RM, Schiffrin EL (2004) Reactive oxygen species in vascular biology: implications in hypertension. *Histochemistry Cell Biology* 122(4): 339–52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-004-0696-7>
- Zheleva-Dimitrova D, Nedialkov P, Girreser U, Kitanov G (2012) Benzophenones and flavonoids from *Hypericum mannulatum* and their antioxidant activities. *Natural product research* 26(17): 1576–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2011.582468>